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MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC CHANGES IN THE SMALL INTESTINE AFTER GENERAL ANESTHESIA IN EXPERIMENTAL COMBINED INJURIES**Tillayev S.S.**

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Resume. General anesthesia is a drug-induced loss of consciousness characterized by controlled depression of the central nervous system and analgesia. It is difficult to quickly awaken a patient from this condition, and sensory, motor, and autonomic reflex functions are significantly suppressed. Combined trauma refers to mechanical injuries involving two or more of the body's seven anatomical regions (head, neck, chest, abdomen, pelvis, spine, limbs). General anesthesia can lead to numerous adverse effects. In particular, it temporarily disrupts gastrointestinal motility after surgery, causes secondary neuromuscular insufficiency, and primarily affects the small intestine, contributing to the development of postoperative intestinal obstruction — a multifactorial and complex condition.

Keywords: combined trauma, general anesthesia, small intestine, morphology, morphometry.

ТАЖРИБАВИЙ ҚЎШМА ЖАРОҲАТЛАРДА УМУМИЙ АНЕСТЕЗИЯДАН КЕЙИНГИ ИНГИЧКА ИЧАКНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ВА МОРФОМЕТРИК ЎЗГАРИШЛАРИ**Тиллаев С.С.**

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Резюме. Умумий анестезия - бу дори воситасидан келиб чиққан онгни йўқотиши бўлиб, марказий асаб тизимининг бошқариладиган депрессияси ва анальгезияси билан тавсифланади. Беморни бу ҳолатдан осонгина чиқариб бўлмайди, ҳиссий, восита ва автоном рефлекс функциялари камайтиради. Комбинацияланган травма деганда тананинг етти анатомик қисмларидан иккитаси ёки ундан ортигида (бош, бўйин, кўкрак, қорин, тос суяги, умуртқа погонаси, оёқ-қўллар) механик шикастланиши тушунилади. Умумий беҳушлик кўплаб ножўя таъсирларни келтириб чиқаради. Хусусан, операциядан кейин ошқозон-ичак моторикасини вақтинча бузади, иккиламчи ривожланадиган асаб-мушак етишмовчилиги келтириб чиқаради ва биринчи навбатда ингичка ичакка таъсир қилади ҳамда мультифакторли ва мураккаб ҳолат бўлган операциядан кейинги ичак тутилишига олиб келади.

Калит сўзлар: қўшма жароҳат, умумий анестезия, ингичка ичак, морфология, морфометрия.

МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И МОРФОМЕТРИЧЕСКИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ТОНКОЙ КИШКИ ПОСЛЕ ОБЩЕЙ АНЕСТЕЗИИ ПРИ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ СОЧЕТАННЫХ ТРАВМАХ**Тиллаев С.С.**

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Резюме. Общая анестезия - это вызванная лекарственными средствами утрата сознания, характеризующаяся контролируемым угнетением центральной нервной системы и анальгезией. Из этого состояния пациента трудно быстро вывести, при этом снижаются чувствительные, двигательные и автономные рефлекторные функции. Под сочетанной травмой понимается механическое повреждение двух и более из семи анатомических областей тела (голова, шея, грудная клетка, живот, таз, позвоночник, конечности). Общая анестезия вызывает множество побочных эффектов. В частности, она временно нарушает моторику желудочно-кишечного тракта после операции, приводит к вторичной нейромышечной недостаточности и прежде всего влияет на тонкую кишку, вызывая послеоперационную кишечную непроходимость - многофакторное и сложное состояние.

Ключевые слова: сочетанная травма, общая анестезия, тонкая кишка, морфология, морфометрия.

Relevance of the research. Combined injuries of the small intestine occur with high frequency in blunt abdominal trauma and are characterized by significant complications and mortality due to the severity of internal organ damage and the difficulty of diagnosis. Small intestine injuries resulting from blunt abdominal trauma account for a considerable portion of all abdominal organ injuries. In modern medicine, various traumatic conditions, particularly combined injuries—those involving simultaneous damage to multiple organs—are among the most frequent and life-threatening clinical scenarios. In such cases, prompt and ef-

fective surgical intervention, along with the appropriate choice of anesthesia methods, is of critical importance.

General anesthesia techniques exert both direct and indirect effects on various body systems, including the small intestine. The small intestine plays a crucial role in nutrient absorption and immune response, which are vital for postoperative recovery. Notably, anesthetic agents may affect the intestinal wall cells and blood circulation, potentially altering the morphological structure of the intestine. Understanding the changes that occur in the small intestine under the influence of anesthesia following combined injuries is an important question in medical practice.

Studying these changes at the morphological level - analyzing tissue processes under a microscope - can aid in preventing complications associated with anesthesia and postoperative outcomes.

The topic of our study serves as a relevant scientific basis for improving surgical practice, individualizing anesthesia strategies, and enhancing postoperative recovery processes.

The purpose of the study: to study the morphological and morphometric changes in the small intestine following general anesthesia in experimental models of combined trauma.

Materials and Methods of the research: In this study, 30 outbred white rats of both sexes, aged 3 and 9 months, with body weights ranging from 110 to 250 grams, were used. Throughout the experiment, strict adherence was maintained to the biosecurity rules and ethical principles outlined in the works of N.A. Nuralliev and colleagues. This included standardized procedures for animal care and grouping. All laboratory animals underwent veterinary screening to exclude potential diseases, and they were quarantined for 21 days to prevent external infections.

The experimental animals were housed in plastic cages placed on racks, with five rats per cage. Each cage was labeled with the number of animals, the experiment start date, and the name of the responsible researcher. The vivarium rooms and cages were cleaned daily in accordance with strict sanitary standards. In the event of an animal's death during the experiment, the carcass was treated with a 20% solution of chlorinated lime and buried following all necessary biosafety procedures. A critical aspect of the study was ensuring adequate care for the laboratory animals, as any disruption in their feeding regimen or hygienic conditions could negatively affect their health, increase susceptibility to disease, and ultimately compromise the accuracy and reliability of the experimental results.

As part of the research project, laboratory rats were divided into two groups:

1. **Control group** (n=15): Outbred white rats with no soft tissue injury to the surface of the right hind limb and not exposed to any general anesthetics.
2. **Experimental group 2** (n=15): Outbred white rats that received a soft tissue injury to the surface of the right hind limb and were subsequently administered the general anesthetic nitrous oxide (N₂O) via inhalation.

1-table

Description of Animal Grouping (n =30)

Group	Descriptions	Number of animals	Body weight of the animals
Control group (n =15)	Outbred white rats with no soft tissue injury to the surface of the right hind limb, and not exposed to local or general anesthetics	7 outbred white rats, 3 months old	110-120 gr.
		8 outbred white rats, months old	200-280 gr
Main experimental group (n = 15)	Outbred white rats that received a soft tissue injury to the surface of the right hind limb, followed by administration of the general anesthetic N ₂ O (nitrous oxide) via inhalation.	8 outbred white rats, 3 months old	110-120 gr.
		7 outbred white rats, 9 months old	200-280 gr

We started our experiment by inducing experimental mechanical injury in 30 outbred white rats aged 3 to 9 months. For this, mechanical injury was applied to the soft tissue of the surface of the right hind limb of the rats, resulting in soft tissue damage.

The next phase of the experiment involved 30 outbred white rats aged 3 to 9 months, where mechanical injury was inflicted on the soft tissue of the right hind limb. After the injury, general anesthesia was applied. The most commonly used anesthetic, N₂O (nitrous oxide), was administered via inhalation. Nitrous oxide is a colorless, odorless, and mildly sweet-tasting gas. It dissolves well in water, blood, and tissue fluids. It is exhaled unchanged through the respiratory system. Nitrous oxide is stored in liquid form in gray steel cylinders, with its gaseous phase pressure around 50 atm. It is used in combination with analge-

sics, relaxants, neuroleptics, and other anesthetics as part of general anesthesia. The next phase of our experiment continued 120 minutes after the administration of the anesthetic.

In the subsequent phase, the experimental animals were euthanized at appropriate time intervals using decapitation. After opening the abdominal cavity, the small intestine was extracted. The width of the small intestine was measured using a millimeter ruler and underwent morphological and morphometric examination.

Results and Conclusions: A series of morphological and morphometric changes were observed in the small intestine (jejunal tissue) of the rats under the influence of general anesthesia. These changes were primarily explained by reduced peristalsis, circulatory disturbances, altered nervous system regulation, and the direct effects of the anesthetic agents used during general anesthesia.

Pic 1. Microscopic appearance of a section of the jejunum from a 9-month-old albino rat under general anesthesia in the experimental group. Stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin. Magnification: 20× objective, 10× ocular. Observation: 1. Destruction of goblet cells and formation of vacuoles.

Morphological Changes in the Jejunum of 3- and 9-Month-Old Rats Following General Anesthesia. In the jejunum of 3- and 9-month-old rats administered general anesthesia, the following morphological alterations were observed:

Villus Height: In 3-month-old rats, the average villus height ranged from 312.1 to 330.9 μm , whereas in 9-month-old rats, it ranged from 372.6 to 389.4 μm . Notably, these measurements were lower compared to the control group.

Crypt Depth: The crypt depth in 3-month-old rats varied between 142.1 and 154.3 μm , and in 9-month-old rats, it ranged from 231.7 to 248.3 μm . These changes are attributed to the slowed intestinal peristalsis and hypoxic alterations induced by the anesthetic agents.

Mucosal Thickness: The thickness of the mucosal layer decreased from 97.3–101.7 μm in 3-month-old rats to 102.4–111.8 μm in 9-month-old rats.

Muscle Layer Thickness: The muscle layer thickness reduced from 113.7–144.9 μm in 3-month-old rats to 133.4–161.7 μm in 9-month-old rats.

Goblet Cell Density and Activity: In specimens stained with Alcian blue, a decrease in mucin density was noted, indicating reduced secretory activity in goblet cells. The number of goblet cells was approximately 133–141 in 3-month-old rats and 142–149 in 9-month-old rats.

Collagen Fiber Accumulation: An increase in collagen fibers was observed in the submucosal and adventitial tissues of 3-month-old rats, staining dark red and suggesting fibrotic responses due to edema and inflammation.

Crypt and Villus Surrounding Tissue Changes: In certain areas, microhemorrhages were detected amid fibrinous and fibrotic changes surrounding the crypts and villi.

In 9-month-old rats, the distribution of collagen fibers was more pronounced, occupying larger areas within the tissue. This indicates ongoing fibrosis associated with intestinal obstruction. In the adventitia and submucosal layers, collagen accumulations were not symmetric and diffuse; instead, they were concentrated in several distinct zones.

In the muscular layer, tissue homogeneity was disrupted, with collagen fibers infiltrating between smooth muscle cells. This infiltration is linked to a reduction in motor function.

Pic 2. Microscopic appearance of a section of the jejunum from a 9-month-old albino rat under general anesthesia in the experimental group. Stained using Van Gieson's method. Magnification: 20× objective, 10× ocular. 1. The majority of the lamina propria is encased by collagen fibers, with normal structure being rarely observed. 2. Collagen fibers extensively surround the crypts and villi.

Pic 3. Microscopic appearance of a section of the jejunum from a 9-month-old albino rat under general anesthesia in the experimental group. Stained using Van Gieson's method. Magnification: 20× objective, 10× ocular. 1. The majority of the lamina propria is encased by collagen fibers, with normal structure being rarely observed. 2. Collagen fibers extensively surround the crypts and villi. 3. Microhemorrhages are present.

Conclusion. Following general anesthesia, the distribution of mucin substances decreased, and the secretory activity of goblet cells declined. In 3-month-old rats, the number of goblet cells ranged between 133–141 within an area of 1,123,633 px², while in 9-month-old rats, the number ranged from 142–149 within an area of 1,123,637 px². This condition is associated with trophic weakening, decreased secretory function, and reduced neural regulation as a result of general anesthesia.

Histological analysis using Van Gieson's stain of the jejunum (a section of the small intestine) in both 3- and 9-month-old rats after general anesthesia revealed that the degree and localization of tissue fibrosis varied depending on age and the type of anesthesia applied. Age-related differences were evident: In 3-month-old rats, after general anesthesia, collagen fibers were predominantly accumulated in the submucosa and lamina propria. This indicates the early stage of fibrosis and reflects enhanced collagen synthesis in response to inflammation. Additionally, the connective tissue architecture was disrupted, and microhemorrhages were observed in certain areas.

In 9-month-old rats, the quantity and area of collagen fiber distribution significantly increased. The fibers were strongly accumulated in multiple zones in a non-symmetric manner, showing a pronounced fibrotic response. Infiltration of collagen fibers into the muscular layer and disruption of tissue homogeneity contributed to decreased peristalsis and motor activity.

After general anesthesia, goblet cell counts ranged from 133–141, and mucin density was reduced. The lamina propria was fully infiltrated by collagen, with fibrotic changes and microhemorrhages observed around the crypts. Collagen infiltration into the muscular layer also increased, resulting in impaired morpho-functional stability.

Furthermore, after general anesthesia, goblet cell counts in 9-month-old rats ranged from 142–149, and mucin distribution was markedly reduced. Collagen accumulation was intense and asymmetrical, with sharply stained zones around crypts displaying microhemorrhages and dystrophic changes. The muscular tissue lost its structural homogeneity, leading to a decline in motor functions.

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